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Grant agreement N. 773139

DELIVERABLE N°6.3

Title: Inventory of validation data available

Validation of diagnostic tests to support plant health

Due date:	Month 4
Actual submission data	<p>Month 6</p> <p>The Description of Work (DOW) stated: <i>'An inventory of validation data available will be performed and the data will be entered in the EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise (validation section) by EPPO. Additional validation data resulting from the project or available in plant pest diagnostic laboratories will be made publicly and freely available through the EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise (section validation data). All partners concerned will contribute to provide such data. The validation database will be maintained by EPPO after the project.'</i></p> <p>When the project was prepared in 2017 the plans were that the survey would be organised in the spring. The delayed start of the project did not allow this to happen. In addition, to avoid multiple surveys, the Steering Committee agreed that surveys to be organised by the different consortia would be done through a limited number of questionnaires. The present survey was consequently aimed at gathering information on the validation data available for the first test performance study (TPS).</p>
Start date of the project	01-05-2018
Deliverable lead contractor (organization name)	EPPO
Participants (Partners short names)	All partners
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Abstract:

Task 6.3: Improvement of the validation section of the free access EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise.

This report summarises the inventory of validation data performed for the 6 pests included in the first Test performance study (TPS). The validation reports collected will be entered in the EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise (validation section).

Partners involved: all partners

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Report - Inventory of validation data available for the 6 pests included in the first TPS.

When the project was prepared in 2017 the plans were that the survey would be organised in the spring. The delayed start of the project did not allow this to happen. In addition, to avoid multiple surveys, the Steering Committee agreed that surveys to be organised by the different consortia would be done through a limited number of questionnaires. The present survey was consequently aimed at gathering information on the validation data available for the first test performance study (TPS).

The EPPO Secretariat circulated links to the survey on the 2018-07-27 with a deadline of the 2018-09-07 (survey length extended compared to the original plans to allow for the summer vacation).

The survey was sent to 66 laboratories in 31 countries. The laboratories were selected from the EPPO Database on Diagnostic Expertise and these laboratories included experts which had declared expertise on one or more of the 6 pests in the first TPS.

For the pests below Part I of the survey aimed to identify which diagnostic tests are used in the different laboratories (and to collect detailed information on the tests, on the tests themselves and the types of samples and matrices used) and to collect validation data in the form of reports on these tests.

- *Erwinia amylovora*,
- *Pantoea stewartii* subsp. *stewartii*,
- *Citrus tristeza virus*,
- *Plum pox virus*,
- *Fusarium circinatum* and
- *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*.

The pdf of the questions in the study are available in Appendix 1.

The full results of the study are available (in an anonymised form) in Appendix 2.

Fig 2. Validation status of all the tests described by respondents during Survey 1

Information was received on the following types of tests: plating (58), IF (11), ELISA (40), conventional PCR (60), real-time PCR (45), conventional RT-PCR (17), real-time RT-PCR (17), LAMP (2), other methods applicable for on-site testing (5), other methods applicable for use in the laboratory (42). Details about the tests were also collected.

Collection of full validation reports

20 tests described were marked as having a validation report already uploaded in the diagnostics database and 17 tests described as having the report ready for upload (to date 10 of these tests had reports marked as ready for upload and were provided to the EPPO Secretariat via the online system, in fact 12 reports were collected as some tests had more than one report provided). Validation data for the reports not yet received will be requested.

The new validation data reports collected during the project are on the following pests/methods/tests:

Pest	Method	Test
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Real-time PCR	Real-time PCR SYBR green
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	Other methods applicable in the laboratory	PCR-sequencing according to PM7/129 - 18S (Holterman <i>et al.</i> 2006 Molecular Biology and Evolution 23, 1792–1800) - 28S (Holterman <i>et al.</i> 2008 Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution 48, 758–763)
<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Plating	NSA, CCT, King B
<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Conventional PCR	PCR according to Stoger <i>et al.</i> (2006)
<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	Real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (Gottsberger, 2010)
<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	Real-time PCR	<i>Fusarium cirinatum</i> , loos <i>et al</i> , 2009
<i>Pantoea stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i>	Other methods applicable in the laboratory	FLASH PCR detection Kit (for fluorescence end-point detection) for detection and identification of <i>P. stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i> from samples of plant and seeds
Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA
Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA
Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA

Of the 10 categories of methods described (i.e. plating, IF, ELISA, conventional PCR, real-time PCR, conventional RT-PCR, real-time RT-PCR, LAMP, other methods applicable for on-site testing, other methods applicable for use in the laboratory) new validation reports were collected for 4 different methods: ELISA, conventional PCR, real-time PCR and other methods applicable for use in the laboratory.

Methods for which new validation reports were collected	Number of new validation reports collected.
ELISA	3
Other methods applicable for use in the laboratory	2
Real-time PCR	3
Conventional PCR,	1
Plating	1

New validation reports were collected on tests on 5 of the 6 pests covered in the study. The new validation reports were collected from 6 countries.

Pests for which new validation reports were collected on the tests described	Number of new validation reports collected.
<i>Erwinia amylovora</i> ,	3
<i>Pantoea stewartii</i> subsp. <i>stewartii</i> ,	1
<i>Plum pox virus</i> ,	3
<i>Fusarium circinatum</i>	1
<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	2

Validation data will be collected for tests for other pests (not those included in the first TPS) during the second survey.

VALITEST
QUESTIONNAIRE
 WP1/WP4/WP6

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°773139.

Accurate and reliable detection and identification of plant pests are essential to avoid or reduce economical costs and trade disruptions and to support surveillance activities. Validation is essential to provide information on the performance of the tests. However, most of detection and identification tests are only validated on an intra-laboratory basis or through limited test performance studies (TPS), and there is a need to further harmonize practices. The VALITEST project aims at producing validation data and will include two rounds of TPS. In the first round, TPS will include the following pests: *Erwinia amylovora*, *Pantoea stewartii* subsp. *stewartii*, *Citrus tristeza virus*, *Plum pox virus*, *Fusarium circinatum* and *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*.

One of the aims of the VALITEST project is to produce validation data by means of test performance studies (TPS) in two different rounds. In the first round, TPS will include the following pests: *Erwinia amylovora*, *Pantoea stewartii*, citrus tristeza virus, plum pox virus, *Fusarium circinatum* and *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*. The TPS will include combinations of pest/test/matrix, prioritized based on the expertise of the project's consortium. The second round will include other pests and test combinations based on the needs expressed by various stakeholders. We are contacting you as experts in plant pest diagnostics for bacteriology, virology, nematology or mycology. We would like to know which diagnostic tests are used and which validation data already exist in the EPP0 region for the prioritized pests. We are kindly asking you to provide data on diagnostic tests and validations (Part I). In addition, we are asking you whether you are willing to participate in TPS study (Part II).

Part I

Q1. For which of the following pests do you perform diagnostic testing:

- Erwinia amylovora*
- Pantoea stewartii* subsp. *stewartii*
- Citrus tristeza virus
- Plum pox virus
- Fusarium circinatum*
- Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*
- None of the above (go to part II)

For each of the chosen pest go to the following questions. First Q2 followed by Q3-Q4-Q5-Q6 and repeat this for each chosen pest.

	Next Go to Q2 (except if none of the above then go to II)
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Q2. Which of the following methods do you use for the diagnostic testing of [pest]:

(only the relevant method will appear in the online questionnaire)

- plating
- IF
- ELISA
- conventional PCR
- real-time PCR
- LAMP
- Other methods applicable for on-site testing
- Other method applicable for use in the laboratory

	Next Go to Q3
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XXXXXX is free text

XXXXXX is single choice (radio button)

Q3.

Q3.1 Pest xxxx Plating

Q 3.1a Plating media used (including the reference if available): free text one plating media at a time

Q 3.1b Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.1c Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.1d Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question will appear)

No (select "add another plating media" or "next")

Q3.1e. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report(s).

No (select "add another plating media" or "next")

Q3.2 Pest xxxx IF

Q 3.2a Name of kits/antibodies, supplier and catalogue no.: free text

Q 3.2b Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.2c Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.2d Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question will appear)

No (select "add another kit/antibodies" or "next")

Q3.2e. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another kit/antibodies" or "next")

Q3.3 Pest xxxx ELISA

Q 3.3a description of the test

Indirect ELISA

DAS-ELISA

DASI-ELISA (also called TAS ELISA),

PTA ELISA (direct and indirect)

Tissue print-ELISA or Direct tissue blot immunoassay

Other type of ELISA test: free text

Q 3.3b Name supplier and catalogue no. of kit/antibodies used: free text

Q 3.3c Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.3d Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.3e Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question should appear)

No (select "add another kit/antibodies" or "next")

Q3.3f. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another kit/antibodies" or "next")

Q3.4 Pest xxxx Conventional PCR

Q 3.4a Name of Conventional PCR test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.4b Name of Primer and Probes: free text

Q 3.4c Name of polymerase/kit, supplier and catalogue no.: free text

Q 3.4d Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.4e Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.4f Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question will appear)

No (select "add another Conventional PCR" or "next")

Q3.4g. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another Conventional PCR" or "next")

Q3.5 Pest xxxx Conventional RT PCR

Q 3.5a Name of Conventional RT PCR test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.5b Name of Primer and Probes: free text

Q 3.5c Name of polymerase/kit, supplier and catalogue no.: free text

Q 3.5d Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.1e Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.5f Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question should appear)

No (select "add another Conventional RT PCR" or "next")

Q3.5g. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another Conventional RT PCR" or "next")

Q3.6 Pest xxxx real-time PCR

Q 3.6a Name of real-time PCR test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.6b Name of Primer and Probes: free text

Q 3.6c Name of polymerase/kit, supplier and catalogue no.: free text

Q 3.6d Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.6e Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.6f Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question should appear)

No (select "add another real-time PCR" or "next")

Q3.6g. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another real-time PCR" or "next")

Q3.7 Pest xxxx real-time RT PCR

Q 3.7a Name of real-time RT PCR test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.7b Name of Primer and Probes: free text

Q 3.7c Name of polymerase/kit, supplier and catalogue no.: free text

Q 3.7d Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.7e Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves

- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.7f Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question should appear)

No (select "add another real-time RT PCR" or "next")

Q3.7g. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another real-time RT PCR" or "next")

Q3.8 Pest xxxx LAMP

Q 3.8a Name of LAMP test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.8b Name supplier and catalogue no. of polymerase/kit used: free text

Q 3.8c Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.8d Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.8e Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question will appear)

No (select "add another LAMP test" or "next")

Q3.8f. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add another LAMP test" or "next")

Q3.9 Pest xxxx Other methods that can be used on-site

Q 3.9a Name of the test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.9b Name supplier and catalogue no. (put not applicable, if not relevant): free text

Q 3.9c Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.9d Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood

- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.9e Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question should appear)

No (select "add an additional Other method that can be used on-site" or "next")

Q3.9f. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add an additional Other method that can be used on-site" or "next")

Q3.10 Pest xxxx Other methods that can be used in the laboratory

Q 3.10a Name of the test used (including the reference if available): free text one test at a time

Q 3.10b Name supplier and catalogue no. (put not applicable, if not relevant): free text

Q 3.10c Test used for

Symptomatic samples

Asymptomatic samples

Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples

Q3.10d Matrix/Matrices used

- Leaves
- Fruit
- Seeds
- Roots
- Herbaceous cuttings
- Woody cuttings
- Wood
- Tubers
- Pure culture
- Soil
- Water
- Other, specify :

Q3.10e Have you validated this [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]

Yes (if yes next question should appear)

No (select "add an additional Other method that can be used in the laboratory" or "next")

Q3.10f. Are you willing to share your validation report for the [method] test for diagnostic testing of [pest]. You may already have shared it through the EPPO database on diagnostic expertise. The validation report can be in your own languages.

Yes -> Already uploaded in the 'EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise'

Yes -> Please upload the report.

No (select "add an additional Other method that can be used in the

Part II

The following questions are included to make an inventory of possible participants in the first round of test performance studies which will be launched in the end of 2018. Samples are planned to be sent in March 2019 and data will be collected in June 2019. Studies will be performed on six pests using different diagnostic tests, which still need to be selected. As participating laboratory, you will receive a set of samples, protocols and the selected chemicals/reagents. However, all other costs, which occur in the course of the study, should be covered by your laboratory. The results will be reported in a confidential manner.

Q4. For which of the the following pest-method combinations are you or your institute potentially interested in participating in a test performance study?

Please fill in your contact information in case we need some extra information about the diagnostic tests and for the possible participation in any test performance study. Your contact details will only be used in the frame of the VALITEST project.

Name:

e-mail:

Appendix 2

Test id	Lab id	Country	Pest	Method	Test Name	Primer and Probes	Supplier	Used for	Matrix	validated	Share
283	167	Austria	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Sensitive and Species-Specific	A and B	Solis Firepol Ready to Use Mix	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	Yes	No
286	167	Austria	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	Conventional PCR with AGE	PST-1, PST-R	Solis Firepol Ready to Use Master	Symptomatic samples	Leaves	Yes	No
288	167	Austria	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR according to	cps-R74F, cps-177R, cps-133	PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix, Quant	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds	Yes	No
285	167	Austria	Pantoea stev	plating	YPGA, EPP0 PM7/60			Symptomatic samples	Leaves	Yes	No
284	167	Austria	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Development and evaluation of	hpEaF, hpEaR, hpEaP	PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix, Quant	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots, Herb	Yes	Yes - repo
281	167	Austria	Erwinia amy	plating	Kings B, PM 7/20 (2)* Erwinia	amylovara		Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots, Herb	Yes	No
191	167	Austria	Citrus tristet	real-time RT-PCR	Bertolini, et al 2008. Quant	3'UTR1, 3'UTR2, 181T	qScript XLT 1-Step RT-qPCR Tougl	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
193	167	Austria	Citrus tristet	real-time RT-PCR	Saponari, M. et al 2008. Qu	P25F, P25R, CTV-, CTV-S,	qScript XLT 1-Step RT-qPCR Tougl	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
196	167	Austria	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	Schneider, W.L., et al 2004.	Forward primer, Reverse Prim	qScript XLT 1-Step RT-qPCR Tougl	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots	No	
197	167	Austria	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	Olmos, A, et al. 2005. Real-	P241 primer, P316D primer, P3	qScript XLT 1-Step RT-qPCR Tougl	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots	No	
190	167	Austria	Citrus tristet	conventional PCR	Roy A. et al, 2005: A multipl	AR18F, AR18R		Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
195	167	Austria	Plum pox vir	conventional PCR	Wetzel, T. et al 1992. A high	P1, P2	QIAGEN OneStep RT-PCR Kit, Qia	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots	No	
160	169	Greece	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Loewe, no 07099	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
165	169	Greece	Citrus tristet	conventional PCR	Nolasco, 2002 (with modifi	CTV1, CTV10	ThermoFisher Scientific, Taq DNA	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No	
167	169	Greece	Citrus tristet	Other methods	High Throughput Sequencing on	si RNAs (Ion Torrent, Illumin	no application	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No	
168	169	Greece	Citrus tristet	ELISA	Indirect ELISA		MCA13 antibodies (IVIA, Spain)	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No	
171	169	Greece	Citrus tristet	ELISA	Tissue print-ELISA or Direct	tissue blot immunoassay	PLANT PRINT Diagnostics, cat no	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No	
235	170	Austria	Fusarium cir	plating	Komada			Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Wood	No	
238	170	Austria	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Morphological identification:	EPP0 diagnostic protocol PM	n/a	Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No	
237	170	Austria	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	ITS RFLP PCR Burgermeister	forward: F194 (5'-CGT-AAC-AA	AccuStart II, Quanta bio, order no	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
148	171	Hungary	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Loewe Biochemica GmbH, Plum	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
172	171	Hungary	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	Spot TaqMan Real-time RT-	P241, P316D, P316M, PPV-DM	TaqMan Universal Master Mix II,	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
150	171	Hungary	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DASI-ELISA (also called TAS	ELISA)	Durviz SL, REAL REALISA PPV-5B	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
149	171	Hungary	Bursaphelen	Other methods	ITS RFLP PCR (Burgermeister	et al., 2009.)		Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood	No	
377	172	Hungary	Erwinia amy	plating	KBN			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit	No	
215	174	Germany	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	real-time PCR, Salm H & G	Primer P29TF and P29TR	Quantifast SYBR Green PCR Kit (C	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Wood, Pure culture	No	
214	174	Germany	Erwinia amy	plating	Kings B and levan (NSA) medium	(see PM7/20(2))		Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
221	174	Germany	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Microscopy (see PM7/4(3))		no application	Both symptomatic and as	Roots, Woody cuttings, W	No	
220	174	Germany	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	ITS RFLP PCR (EPP0 PM7/4)	ITSn-1 and ITSn-2	HotStar Taq Master Mix Kit (Qia)	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No	
217	174	Germany	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Agglutination test (see PM7/20(2))			Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No	
230	174	Germany	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (PM 7/60 (2)	primer cps-R74F and cps-177	TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Mast	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds, Pure culture	No	
218	174	Germany	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		PRI (Wageningen Plant Research	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
331	175	Italy	Plum pox vir	conventional PCR	La Sharka delle Drupacee -	P 1, P2	Go Taq G2 Flexi DNA Polymerase	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	cuttings, Woody cuttings,	
259	175	Italy	Erwinia amy	plating	CT medium (Ishimaru & Klos,	1984)		Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Wood, shoots	Yes	No
333	175	Italy	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	Olmos A. et al. - Real-time	PPV 241, PPV 316D, PPV316M	TaqMan RNA-to-Ct 1-Step Kit App	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	cuttings, Woody cuttings,	
352	176	Slovakia	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	Schweiggkofler et al., 2004;	primers CIRC1A, CIRC4A / prim	MyTaq DNA polymerase, Bionline,	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No	
353	176	Slovakia	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	Burgermeister et al., 2009	primers BXYF, BXR	MyTaq DNA polymerase, Bionline,	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No	
349	176	Slovakia	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Taylor et al., 2001	G1-F, G1-R	MyTaq DNA polymerase, Bionline,	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings, W	No	
341	176	Slovakia	Erwinia amy	plating	KingB, levan			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
351	176	Slovakia	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Pirc et al., 2009	Ams116F, Ams189R, Ams141T	labTaq Green Mix Lo Rox, Labte	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
345	176	Slovakia	Erwinia amy	IF			Loewe (Biochemica GmbH), poly	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
343	177	Slovakia	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	EPP0 PM7/20 - Pirc et al (2	Ams116F, Ams189R, Ams141T	TaqMan™ Universal PCR Master	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	Yes	No
337	177	Slovakia	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	EPP0 PM7/20 - Bereswill	Bereswill - A,B, Taylor G1F, G2	DreamTaq DNA polymerase, EP07	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	Yes	No
338	179	Bulgaria	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Reagent set Alkaline Phosphatase	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
243	179	Bulgaria	Bursaphelen	real-time PCR	Francois et al., 2007	BsatF, BsatRV, BsatS	TaqMan® Universal Master Mix II	Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No	
245	179	Bulgaria	Erwinia amy	plating	KBM, NSA and CCT			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
246	179	Bulgaria	Pantoea stev	plating	NBY, YPGA, KBM			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds, Herbaceous	No	
247	179	Bulgaria	Fusarium cir	plating	SNA, DCPA, PDAS			Symptomatic samples	Seeds, Woody cuttings, W	No	
248	179	Bulgaria	Fusarium cir	Other methods	morphological identification			Symptomatic samples	Woody cuttings, Wood, P	No	
249	179	Bulgaria	Erwinia amy	Other methods	biochemical tests, hypersensitivity	and pathogenicity tests		Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
250	179	Bulgaria	Pantoea stev	Other methods	biochemical tests and pathogenicity	tests		Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
244	179	Bulgaria	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Identification on the basis of	morphological features	no application	Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No	
330	179	Bulgaria	Erwinia amy	IF			polyclonal antiserum from Loewe	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
332	179	Bulgaria	Pantoea stev	IF			polyclonal antiserum from Loewe	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Seeds, Herbaceous	No	
344	179	Bulgaria	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Reagent set Alkaline Phosphatase	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
357	180	Belgium	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Plan Print Diagnostics S.L.	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	Yes	No
207	182	Italy	Plum pox vir	LAMP	RT-LAMP PPV		'Ready-to-use' Master Mix, Hyris	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	Yes	Yes - repo
175	182	Italy	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	PCR of Taylor et al., 2001	G1-F: 5'-CCT GCA TAA ATC ACC	G2-C: GAC AGC TCA ATG-3' G2-R: 5'	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
192	182	Italy	Citrus tristet	real-time RT-PCR	TaqMan real-time RT-PCR (P	Primers 3'UTR1/3'UTR2, Probe	TaqMan™ RNA-to-CT™ 1-Step Kit	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
174	182	Italy	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	nested PCR of Lop et al (20	AJ75, AJ76, PEANT1, PEANT2	Go Taq flexi DNA polymerase Pro	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
205	182	Italy	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	TaqMan real-time RT-PCR (P	Primers P241/P316D/P316M,	TaqMan™ RNA-to-CT™ 1-Step Kit	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Wood	Yes	Yes - repo
265	182	Italy	Fusarium cir	real-time PCR	dual-labelled probe real tim	Primers: FCIR-F, FCIR-R and P	Mastermix Sensimix II Probe (Bio	Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Wood	Yes	No
151	182	Italy	Erwinia amy	plating	EPP0 standard PM7/20 (2)			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
203	182	Italy	Plum pox vir	conventional PCR	One-step RT-PCR	P1/P2 (Wetzel et al, 1991)	GoTaq DNA Polymerase, Promega	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Wood	Yes	Yes - repo
201	182	Italy	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Plum pov virus (PPV), Bioreba, Ca	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Wood	Yes	Yes - repo
185	182	Italy	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	PCR of Coplin & Majerczak	ES16; ESIG2c:	IMMOLASE™ DNA Polymerase, Bionline, code BIO-21046/7/	Pure culture	No		
184	182	Italy	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	PCR AGES see EPP0 Stand	PST-1, PST-R	Platinum™ Taq DNA Polymerase, code 10966026	Pure culture	No		
188	182	Italy	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Real-time (TaqMan) of Tan	Primers: cps-R74F, cps-177R	SSoAdvanced™ Universal Probes Supermix, code: 172-5280	Pure culture	No		
186	182	Italy	Citrus tristet	conventional PCR	One-step RT-PCR	P20-f/r (Rubio et al., 2001)	GoTaq DNA Polymerase, Promega	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
183	182	Italy	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Citrus tristeza virus (CTV), Bioreb	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No	
173	182	Italy	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	PCR of Bereswill et al. (199	A: 5'-CGG TT TTA ACG CTG CG	Go Taq flexi DNA polymerase Pro	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No	
336	185	Spain	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	Burgermeister et al 2009	Forward/Ferris et al 1993) and	Platinum Taq DNA polymerase (In	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	Yes	No
342	185	Spain	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Pirc et al 2009	Ams116F, Ams189R and Ams1	TaqMan universal master mix (A)	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
335	185	Spain	Erwinia amy	ELISA	DASI-ELISA (also called TAS	ELISA)	Protocolo deteccion Ea , ELISA -	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
340	185	Spain	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Taylor et al 2001, Llop et a	G1-F & G2-R ; Peant1, Peant2	Platinum Taq DNA polymerase (In	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
334	185	Spain	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	Burgermeister et al 2009	Ferris & X26 S	Ilustra TM Pure taq Ready -to-go	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	Yes	No
350	185	Spain	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	Schweiggkofler et al 2004	CIRC1 A(f) and CIRC4 A (r)	Platinum Taq DNA polymerase (In	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No	
268	185	Spain	Fusarium cir	plating	PDA, K (komada), SNA			Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Roots, Woody cutti	No	
329	185	Spain	Erwinia amy	plating	CCT and KB			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No	
328	185	Spain	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Morphology			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood	Yes	No
64	186	Finland	Erwinia amy	plating	KB, CCT, Levan, SNA			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
66	186	Finland	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Llop, P., Bonaterrea, A., Perf	AJ75, AJ76, PEANT1, PEANT2	Taq DNA Polymerase, recombinat	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
65	186	Finland	Erwinia amy	IF			PlantPrint Diagnostics Specific m	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	cuttings, Woody cuttings,	
77	186	Finland	Bursaphelen	real-time PCR	François, C., Castagnone, C.	Primers: PsaTF, PsaTRV; Probe	Hot GoldStar Taq (Eurogentec RT	Symptomatic samples	Other larvae, adults	Yes	Yes - repo
81	186	Finland	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	Schweiggkofler, W., O'Donn	CIRC1A, CIRC4A	Platinum Taq-polymerase (5 U/)	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
83	186	Finland	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	MacKenzie, D. J., McLean, M	Primers: P1, P2; Probe.	SuperScript One-Step RT-PCR with	Platinum Taq, -Invitrogen	10928-042	No	
82	186	Finland	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Plum pox potyvirus universal, Lo	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
86	186	Finland	Plum pox vir	conventional PCR	MacKenzie, D. J., McLean, M	P1, P2	SuperScript III RT/Platinum Taq M	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
76	186	Finland	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Pirc, M., Ravnikar, M., Ton	Primers: Ams116F, Ams189R,	QSupermix (Bio Rad) Cat. 170-88	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No	
239	187	United Kin	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Lateral Flow Device - Erwinia	amylovara	Pocket Diagnostic; ERW001980	Symptomatic samples	Herbaceous cuttings, Wod	No	
120	187	United Kin	Erwinia amy	plating	Sucrose Nutrient Agar (SNA),	King's Media B, (Lelliott and	Stead 1987) SNA + Nystatin	Both symptomatic and as	Herbaceous cuttings, Wod	No	
240	187	United Kin	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Lateral Flow Device - Erwinia	amylovara	Pocket Diagnostic; ERW001980	Both symptomatic and as	Herbaceous cuttings, Wod	No	
241	187	United Kin	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Real time PCR (Tambong et	cps-R74F, cps-177R, probe: c	Supplier: Thermo Fisher Scientific	Asymptomatic samples	Seeds	No	
356	187	United Kin	Fusarium cir	real-time PCR	Fusarium cirinum, loo et al	et al, 2009	TaqMan® Environmental Master	Asymptomatic samples	Seeds	Yes	Yes - repo
252	187	United Kin	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Morphology and DNA Sequencing	using CO1		Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, P	Yes	No
208	187	United Kin	Plum pox vir	conventional PCR	PPV RT-PCR, Wetzel T, Can	P1 and P2	Verso 1-Step RT-PCR Kit ReddyM	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit	No	
206	187	United Kin	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Bioreba PPV DAS-ELISA 150512	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit	No	
209	187	United Kin	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Citrus tristeza virus DAS ELISA, A	Both symptomatic and			

118	188	Russian Fed	Pantoea stev	Other methods	FLASH PCR detection Kit (for fluorescence end-point detection)	DNA-Technology, Russia	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Seeds, Herbaceous	Yes	Yes - repo
79	188	Russian Fed	Bursaphelen	Other methods	applicable in the laboratory					
119	188	Russian Fed	Pantoea stev	Other methods	sequencing		Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
272	189	Italy	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Bereswill et al.	AJ75 primer/AJ76 primer	GoTaq DNA Polymerase Green M	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, Pu	No
270	189	Italy	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		CTV DAS-ELISA kit, DSMZ, AS0988	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
273	189	Italy	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Salm and Geider, 2004	P29f primer/ P29 tr primer;	SSOAdvanced Universal probe, Bi	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, Pu	No
269	189	Italy	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PC	Olmos et al. (2005)	P241 primer, P316D primer, P	SSOAdvanced Universal probe, Bi	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
271	189	Italy	Erwinia amy	plating	NSA (Scottichini, 1995)			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, Pu	No
277	189	Italy	Pantoea stev	plating	NBY (Schaad et al., 2001)			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Seeds	No
276	189	Italy	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	Schweigkofler, 2004	Circ1A/ CIRC4A	GoTaq DNA Polymerase Green M	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings	No
274	189	Italy	Erwinia amy	plating	CCT (Ishimaruuklos, 1998)			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, Pu	No
267	189	Italy	Bursaphelen	Other methods	EPP0 PM 7/4 (3) Bursaphelenchus xylophilus			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, V	No
279	189	Italy	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Tambong et al., 2008	CPSrT74f primer/ CPS177r prim	SSOAdvanced Universal probe, Bi	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Seeds	No
278	189	Italy	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	Coplin et al., 2002	ES16/ ESIG2C	GoTaq DNA Polymerase Green M	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Seeds	No
275	189	Italy	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Llop et al. 2000	A primer/B primer	GoTaq DNA Polymerase Green M	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, Pu	No
266	189	Italy	Fusarium cir	plating	Potato Dextrose Agar			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood	No
55	190	Slovenia	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR		CIRC1A, CIRC4A	AmpliTaq Gold 360, Applied Bios	Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Wood, vectors	No
54	190	Slovenia	Fusarium cir	plating				Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Wood, Pure culture	No
178	192	Portugal	Fusarium cir	plating	Appendix 1 PM7/91(1) (PDAS, DCPA, SNA)			Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Roots, Herbaceous	No
156	192	Portugal	Erwinia amy	plating	CCT (Ishimaru & Klos, 1984)			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
157	192	Portugal	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Appendix 10 PM7/20(2)	FER1F/ RGER2R	Go TaqG2 Flexi DNA Polymerase/	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
159	192	Portugal	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Appendix 12 and 13 PM7/2	Ams116F/Ams189R/Ams141T	Maxima Probe qPCR MasterMix/	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	Yes
163	192	Portugal	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Bioassays on immature fruits and young twigs		Appendix VI PM7/20 (1)	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	Yes
164	192	Portugal	Pantoea stev	plating	Appendix 1 PM7/60(2)			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No
211	192	Portugal	Citrus tristet	conventional RT-PCR	one tube, Nolasco	CTV1/CTV10	Go TaqG2 Flexi DNA Polymerase/	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No
170	192	Portugal	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Appendix 5 PM7/60(2)	cps-RT74f/cps-177R/cps-133	Maxima Probe qPCR MasterMix/	Both symptomatic and as	OtherDNA seed extracts	No
169	192	Portugal	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	Appendix 3 PM7/60(2)	PST1/PSTR	Go TaqG2 Flexi DNA Polymerase/	Both symptomatic and as	OtherDNA seed extracts	No
210	192	Portugal	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		CTV Complete kit 480, 1 kit/Biore	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No
42	192	Portugal	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Identification on the basis of morphological features - PM	N.A.		Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, ba	Yes
180	192	Portugal	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	Appendix 4 PM7/91(1) (Sch	CIRC1A / CIRC4A	Go TaqG2 Flexi DNA Polymerase/	Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Pure culture	No
181	192	Portugal	Fusarium cir	real-time PCR	Appendix 4 and 6 PM7/91(1)	CIRC1A / CIRC4A; FCIR-F/FCIR-	Maxima Probe qPCR MasterMix/	Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Pure culture	Yes
182	192	Portugal	Fusarium cir	real-time PCR	Appendix 4 and 6 PM7/91(1)	CIRC1A / CIRC4A; FCIR-F/FCIR-	Maxima Probe qPCR MasterMix/	Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Pure culture	Yes
194	192	Portugal	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	Ribeiro et al. 2012 with prim	ITS1/ITS2	DreamTaq PCR Master, Thermo	Both symptomatic and as	Othersuspected nematode	Yes
212	192	Portugal	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		K-10B AGRITEST	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttin	No
51	193	Germany	Pantoea stev	plating	NBY			Both symptomatic and as	Seeds	No
53	193	Germany	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Agglutination test		non-commercial antibody	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No
47	193	Germany	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Loewe Biochemica, 07186, univer	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Seeds	Yes
49	193	Germany	Erwinia amy	plating	SNA 5%			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	Yes
52	193	Germany	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	PCR on galE gene (Gehring	DC283galE/ DC283galEc	Multiplex PCR Plus Kit, Qiagen, ca	Both symptomatic and as	Seeds	Yes
50	193	Germany	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Ea AgriStrip		Bioreba	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	Yes
43	195	Italy	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		AgriTest	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
358	195	Italy	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	EPP0 7/4 Appendix 1 (Bur	Primer ITS: forward, 26s		Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No
45	195	Italy	Citrus tristet	Other methods	applicable for on-site testing		Life Technologies	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	Yes
44	195	Italy	Citrus tristet	real-time RT-PCR	Yokomi et al., 2008	CP25F/R CP25 probe	Life Technologies	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	Yes
316	195	Italy	Citrus tristet	real-time RT-PCR	qRT-PCR Yokomi, R. K., Sap	CP27F/R CP27-probe	Biorad or Qanta or Life Technol	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No
317	195	Italy	Citrus tristet	real-time RT-PCR	qRT-PCR, Saponari et al 20	CP25F/R CP25 probe	Biorad or Qanta or Life Technol	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No
315	195	Italy	Citrus tristet	Other methods	DTBIA			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings	No
365	195	Italy	Bursaphelen	LAMP	Optigene		kit Isothermal mastermix iso-002	Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No
364	195	Italy	Bursaphelen	real-time PCR	EPP0 7/4 Appendix 3 (Frar	BsATf/BsATRv and BsATs	Applied Biosystem or other vendor	Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No
140	196	Spain	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Gottsberger, 2010	hpEaf and hpEaR. And hpEaP	(Biotools)	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
136	196	Spain	Erwinia amy	plating	King's B, CCT and Levan solid media (EPP0, 2013) and also		liquid King's B and CCT media (EP	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
138	196	Spain	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Taylor et al. (2001)	G1-F and G2-R	Biotools	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
137	196	Spain	Erwinia amy	ELISA	DASI-ELISA (also called TAS ELISA)		Commercial kit of Plant Print Diag	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
139	196	Spain	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Pirc et al., 2009	Ams116F and Ams189R. And	ABiotools	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	No
162	198	Slovenia	Plum pox vir	real-time RT-PCR	real time PCR upon https://	available on: https://www.dlib.si	available on: https://www.dlib.si	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings, fi	No
146	198	Slovenia	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Bioreba AG, all info available on:	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings	No
147	198	Slovenia	Plum pox vir	conventional RT-PCR	IC RT-PCR, modified upon v	for reverse transcription: PPV	M-MLV RT (Promeg; M1701); RN	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings, fi	No
161	198	Slovenia	Plum pox vir	conventional RT-PCR	one step RT-PCR based on	PPV1 ACCGAGACCACACTCACTC	AMV reverse transcriptase (Prom	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Woody cuttings, b	No
312	199	Spain	Erwinia amy	plating	Medios de cultivo kingB, NSA y CCT, elaborados según protocolo EPP0 (PM7/20(2)			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots, Herba	No
306	199	Spain	Erwinia amy	ELISA	Other type of ELISA testDASI-ELISA enriquecido		Kit Plant Print Diagnostics	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots, Herba	No
308	199	Spain	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	PCR en tiempo real (Pirc e	Cebadores: Ams116F: 5'-TCC	Master mix TAKARA nº catalogo:	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No
309	199	Spain	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Nested PCR (Llop et al., 20	Cebadores externos AJ75: 5'-C	Kit Ready-To-GoPCR Beads, GE H	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No
310	199	Spain	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DASI-ELISA (also called TAS ELISA)		Kit de REAL (Inmunoglobulinas p	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Roots, Herba	No
314	199	Spain	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Extracción por embudo Baerman e identificación morfológica siguiendo lo descrito en PM	7		Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Woody cuttings, W	No
313	199	Spain	Fusarium cir	plating	PDA, Komada y SNA. Medios elaborados siguiendo el protocolo descrito en PM7/91(1)			Both symptomatic and as	Seeds, Woody cuttings, W	No
233	202	Germany	Erwinia amy	plating	PM 7/20 (2) Erwinia amylovora			Symptomatic samples	Woody cuttings	No
229	202	Germany	Fusarium cir	Other methods	ISTA 7-009			Symptomatic samples	Seeds	No
234	202	Germany	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	PM 7/20 (2) Erwinia amylovora	Bereswill et al., 1992		Symptomatic samples	Woody cuttings	Yes
232	202	Germany	Bursaphelen	Other methods	EPP0 standard 7/4 (3) visual morphological test			Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No
153	203	Romania	Plum pox vir	conventional RT-PCR	IC-RT-PCR	P1, P2 (Wetzel et al, 1991)	Platinum taq DNA polymerase, In	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cutti	No
152	203	Romania	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	PCR conventional Taylor et	G1-F, G2-R	Platinum taq DNA polymerase, In	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No
104	203	Romania	Erwinia amy	plating	NSA, CCT, King B			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	Yes
107	203	Romania	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	ITS-RFLP Burgermeister et	ITS 1, ITS 2	taqDNA polymerase, QBiogene E	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood	No
155	203	Romania	Pantoea stev	plating	King B			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Seeds, Pure culture	No
122	203	Romania	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Plum pox virus (PPV)/ BIOREBA	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous	Yes
154	203	Romania	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	PCR conventional Schweig	CIRC 1A, CIRC 4A	Platinum taq DNA polymerase, In	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood, Pu	No
105	203	Romania	Fusarium cir	plating	PDA, DCPA, OA, SNA PM 7/91 (1)			Symptomatic samples	Seeds, Herbaceous cuttin	No
158	203	Romania	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	PCR conventional, Coplin a	ES16, ESIG2c	Platinum taq DNA polymerase, In	Both symptomatic and as	Pure culture	No
106	203	Romania	Bursaphelen	Other methods	morphological identification			Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Wood	No
89	206	Georgia	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Morphological			Both symptomatic and as	Wood, stems	No
96	206	Georgia	Plum pox vir	Other methods	AgriStrip Plum pox virus		Bioreba	Both symptomatic and as	OtherBlossoms, leaves and	No
91	206	Georgia	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		IgG Plum pox virus (PPV), Bioreba	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Bark, petioles, pedic	No
90	206	Georgia	Citrus tristet	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		IgG Citrus tristeza virus (CTV), Bi	Both symptomatic and as	OtherBark, petioles, pedic	No
94	206	Georgia	Erwinia amy	Other methods	Erwinia amylovora AgriStrip		Bioreba	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, stems, petio	No
92	206	Georgia	Bursaphelen	Other methods	Extraction			Both symptomatic and as	Wood	No
73	206	Georgia	Erwinia amy	plating	King's B medium			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Pure culture	No
87	206	Georgia	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	ITS RFLP PCR- Burgermeister	5'- CGT AAC AAG GTA GCT GTA G -3 (Ferris et al., 1993)		Both symptomatic and as	Wood, stems	No
88	206	Georgia	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	Conventional PCR targeting	5'- TTT CAC TCG CCG TTA CTA AGG -3 (Vrain, 1993)		Both symptomatic and as	Wood, stems	No
84	206	Georgia	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	PCR according to Taylor et	G1-F: 5'-CCT GCA ATC ACC	Platinum PCR Super Mix (Invitrog	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Pure culture	No
72	206	Georgia	Erwinia amy	plating	Levan medium			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves, Fruit, Pure culture	No
282	207	Latvia	Erwinia amy	IF			Indirect immunofluorescence for	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings	No
290	207	Latvia	Pantoea stev	plating	King's B medium supplemented with nystatin (Reference: EPP0 Diagnostic protokol PM 7/6)			Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
69	207	Latvia	Erwinia amy	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (Gottsberge	hpEaf, hpEaR, hpEaP	Rotor-Gene Probe PCR kit, Qiage	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Pure cul	No
71	207	Latvia	Bursaphelen	conventional PCR	Multiplex PCR (Matsunaga	XF/XR, MF/ FR,	Hot StarTaq DNA polymerase, Qi	Symptomatic samples	Othernematoes	No
67	207	Latvia	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Nested PCR test (Llop et al.	PEANT1, PEANT2; AJ75, AJ76	Hot StarTaq DNA polymerase, Qi	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Pure cul	No
63	207	Latvia	Erwinia amy	plating				Symptomatic samples	Woody cuttings	No
68	207	Latvia	Erwinia amy	conventional PCR	Conventional PCR (Gottsbe	FER1-F, rgER2R	Hot StarTaq DNA polymerase, Qi	Both symptomatic and as	Woody cuttings, Pure cul	No
213	207	Latvia	Fusarium cir	conventional PCR	Conventional PCR (modifie	CIRC1A, CIRC4A	5x HOT FIREPol Blend Master Mix	Asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No
70	207	Latvia	Pantoea stev	conventional PCR	Conventional PCR (modifie	ES16, ESIG2c	Hot StarTaq DNA polymerase, Qi	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Pure culture	No
141	207	Latvia	Plum pox vir	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Bioreba, Cat.No. 150572; Neogen	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
142	207	Latvia	Plum pox vir	conventional RT-PCR	RT-PCR (Wetzel et al. 1991)	General PPV detection (P1-P2)	RNeasy Plant Mini Kit - Qiagen, C	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
145	207	Latvia	Fusarium cir	plating	Dichloran Chloramphenicol	Peptone Agar (DCPA) (modified by loos et al., 2004; after Andre		Asymptomatic samples	Seeds	No
280	207	Latvia	Erwinia amy	plating	Sucrose nutrient agar (SNA) or Levan medium			Symptomatic samples	Woody cuttings	No
289	207	Latvia	Pantoea stev	IF			Immunofluorescence Pantoea ste	Both symptomatic and as	Leaves	No
303	208	France	Pantoea stev	real-time PCR	Tambong JT, Mwange KN, c	cps-RT74f / cps-177R / cps 133	Taqman master mix (ABI)	Asymptomatic samples	Seeds, Pure culture	Yes
299	208	France	Erwinia amy	plating	King B + cycloheximide.			Symptomatic samples	Woody cuttings	No
304	208	France	Erwinia amy	plating	King B + cycloheximide. Possibility to use NSA + cycloheximide or CCT			Symptomatic samples	Herbaceous cuttings, Pure	

74	209	France	Bursaphelenchus	real-time PCR	François (Francois et al. 2008)	BSatF, BsatR et BsatS	kit LightCycler® 480 Probes Master	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Otherwood or wood products	Yes	Yes - repo
131	211	France	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		SRA - 31505, AGDIA	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
133	211	France	Plum pox virus	real-time RT-PCR	MA 043 - Olmos et al. 2007	P241 - P316D - P316 M - PPV-1	Multiscribe Reverse Transcriptase	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	
129	211	France	Citrus tristeza virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		CT-SRA, SEDIAG	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves	No	
58	212	France	Fusarium circinatum	plating	DCPA medium (according to EPPO PM 7/91(1): Gibberella circinata)			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Roots, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
56	212	France	Fusarium circinatum	plating	DCPA medium (according to EPPO PM 7/91(1): Gibberella circinata)			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Roots, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
57	212	France	Fusarium circinatum	real-time PCR	real-time PCR (loos et al. 2007)	FCIR-F, FCIR-R, FCIR-P	qPCR Core kit No Rox (Eurogentec)	Asymptomatic samples	Seeds	Yes	Yes - repo
59	212	France	Fusarium circinatum	Other methods	Sequence analysis of several phylogenetic markers (EF1alpha, RPB2)			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	Yes - repo
99	214	Malta	Fusarium circinatum	plating	Potato Dextrose agar & Water agar			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Woody cuttings, Wood	No	
97	214	Malta	Citrus tristeza virus	ELISA	Tissue print-ELISA or Direct tissue blot immunoassay		Plantprint N/A	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Herbaceous cuttings, Wood	No	
98	214	Malta	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		LOEWE 07186C/480	Asymptomatic samples	Leaves	No	
295	216	Slovenia	Pantoea stevensii	IF			Linaris	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
291	216	Slovenia	Erwinia amylovora	plating	King's B, CCT			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
292	216	Slovenia	Erwinia amylovora	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR described by (Pirc, 2009)	ITS, AmsC (Pirc, 2009)		Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
293	216	Slovenia	Erwinia amylovora	Other methods	Agglutination, pathogenicity test, enrichment		Applied Biosystems mastermix not relevant	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	Yes	No
294	216	Slovenia	Pantoea stevensii	plating	General media			Symptomatic samples	Leaves	No	
296	216	Slovenia	Pantoea stevensii	conventional PCR	AGES - 16S rRNA (EPPO)	AGES - 16S rRNA	/	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds, Pure culture	Yes	No
297	216	Slovenia	Pantoea stevensii	real-time PCR	Tambong, 2008 - cpsD	Tambong, 2008 - cpsD	Applied Biosystems mastermix	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds, Pure culture	Yes	Yes - repo
298	216	Slovenia	Pantoea stevensii	Other methods	MALDI-TOF		not relevant	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	Yes - repo
128	218	Netherlands	Bursaphelenchus	Other methods	PCR-sequencing according to PM7/129 - 18S (Holtermann et al. 2007)		Phusion® High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Othersingle fished nematode	Yes	Yes - repo
263	218	Netherlands	Erwinia amylovora	IF			Serum IPO 7043-7072 (IPO is now no application)	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
189	218	Netherlands	Erwinia amylovora	Other methods	Pathogenicity test on young fruits of Pyrus			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
262	218	Netherlands	Erwinia amylovora	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR described by (Ams116F, Ams189R, Ams141T)		TaqMan Universal PCR Master Mix II	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
127	218	Netherlands	Bursaphelenchus	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR SYBR green		Bursaphelenchus xylophilus specific	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Other1-10 fished nematode	Yes	Yes - repo
264	218	Netherlands	Fusarium circinatum	plating	DCPA (Seeds, asymptomatic); KA, SNA, WA, PDA, DCPA (Wood, symptomatic); SNA, PDA (Purification)		V-PPV-CO and V-PPV-AP, Prime d	Symptomatic samples	Leaves	No	No
260	218	Netherlands	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA			Symptomatic samples	Leaves	No	
187	218	Netherlands	Erwinia amylovora	plating	King's B, Levan, CCT (only for asymptomatic samples, which are very rare)			Symptomatic samples	Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
261	218	Netherlands	Citrus tristeza virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Citrus tristeza virus IgG/Citrus tristeza virus	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit	No	
322	221	Lithuania	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Plum pox virus Reagent set, BIORAD	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
321	221	Lithuania	Erwinia amylovora	Other methods	pathogenicity, hypersensitivity, EPPO PM 7/20 (2)		not applicable	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
325	221	Lithuania	Fusarium circinatum	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (loos et al., 2007)	FCIR-F, FCIR-R, FCIR-P	TaqMan Universal Master Mix II	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
324	221	Lithuania	Fusarium circinatum	plating	DCPA, PDA, SNA, EPPO PM7/91(1)			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Seeds, Roots, Woody cuttings	Yes	No
326	221	Lithuania	Bursaphelenchus	Other methods	Baermann, morphological-morphometric tests, EPPO PM 7/20 (2)		not applicable	Symptomatic samples	Wood, WPM	No	
318	221	Lithuania	Erwinia amylovora	plating	CCT, Levan, King's B			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
319	221	Lithuania	Erwinia amylovora	IF			IVIA (Spain) monoclonal	Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
348	221	Lithuania	Erwinia amylovora	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (Pirc M, Ravaglia et al. 2007)	Ams116F, Ams189R, Ams141T	TaqMan Universal Master Mix II	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
320	221	Lithuania	Erwinia amylovora	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (Gottsberger et al. 2007)	hpEaF, hpEaR, hpEaP	TaqMan Universal Master Mix II	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
327	221	Lithuania	Bursaphelenchus	Other methods	PCR-RFLP, Burgermeister W, Braasch H, Metge K, Gu J, Seifried H, et al. 2007		Primer set: forward (Ferris et al., 2007)	Symptomatic samples	Other nematodes	No	
323	221	Lithuania	Plum pox virus	conventional RT-PCR	Conventional RT PCR (Levy, 2004)	3'NCR sense, 3'NCR antisense	Taq DNA polymerase (recombinant)	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
376	222	Germany	Fusarium circinatum	real-time PCR	Schweigkofler et al., 2004	Circ1A, Circ4A	qPCR Mastermix SybrGreen (Applied Biosystems)	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds	No	
373	222	Germany	Erwinia amylovora	conventional PCR	Beresswill et al. (1992)	A: 5'-CGG TTT TTA ACG CTG G	Promega GoTaq G2	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Woody cuttings, Pure culture	No	
375	222	Germany	Pantoea stevensii	real-time PCR	Tambong et al., 2007	cpRT74F, cps177R, cps133 (p)	InnuMix qPCR Mastermix (Analytik Jena)	Asymptomatic samples	Seeds	Yes	
374	222	Germany	Pantoea stevensii	IF			Erwinia stewartii monoclonal (Linaris)	Asymptomatic samples	Seeds	Yes	
134	222	Germany	Erwinia amylovora	plating	NSA			Symptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Pure culture	No	
177	224	Germany	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		IgG 150512, conj 150522, BIOREBA	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit	Yes	Yes - repo
135	224	Germany	Erwinia amylovora	conventional PCR	Stoger et al., 2006	PEANT1 / PEANT 2		Asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
179	224	Germany	Plum pox virus	conventional RT-PCR	Wetzel et al, 1991	P1 / P2	One Step Kit, Qiagen 210212	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit	No	
176	224	Germany	Erwinia amylovora	conventional PCR	Stoger et al., 2006	PEANT 1 / PEANT 2	Extract-N-Amp Plant PCR kit, Sigma	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Woody cuttings	No	
125	225	United Kingdom	Erwinia amylovora	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR (Gottsberger et al. 2007)	hpEaF, hpEaR, hpEaP	JUMPSTART TAQ READYMIX FOR PCR	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Herbaceous cuttings, Wood	No	
123	225	United Kingdom	Erwinia amylovora	plating	Levan Medium, King's B medium (King et al., 1954).		PM 7/20 (2)* Erwinia amylovora	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Herbaceous cuttings, Wood	No	
124	225	United Kingdom	Erwinia amylovora	conventional PCR	Nested PCR (Llop et al., 2007)	Llop - PEANT1, PEANT2, AJ75	JUMPSTART(TM) REDTAQ(R) REAL TIME PCR	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Herbaceous cuttings, Wood	No	
242	226	Germany	Bursaphelenchus	Other methods	microscopy			Symptomatic samples	Wood	No	
48	228	Czechia	Bursaphelenchus	Other methods	Baermann funnel			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Wood	No	
204	228	Czechia	Pantoea stevensii	conventional PCR	Coplin and Majerczak 2002	ES16, ESIG2c	Biotools DNA polymerase	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	Yes	Yes - repo
199	228	Czechia	Erwinia amylovora	conventional PCR	Beresswill et al 1992	A, B	DNA polymerase, Biotools	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	Yes - repo
347	228	Czechia	Plum pox virus	Other methods	Immunocapture PCR method (Wetzel et al. 1992)		Promega reverse transcriptase, Biorad	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit	No	
354	228	Czechia	Fusarium circinatum	plating	PDA			Symptomatic samples	Seeds, Roots, Woody cuttings	No	
355	228	Czechia	Fusarium circinatum	conventional PCR	Conventional PCR (W. Schwabe et al. 2007)	CIRC1A, CIRC4A	Biotools, TH polymerase	Symptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
198	228	Czechia	Erwinia amylovora	plating	NA, KING, CCT			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
346	228	Czechia	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Bioreba	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit	Yes	Yes - repo
202	228	Czechia	Pantoea stevensii	plating	NA, KING			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Seeds, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
200	228	Czechia	Erwinia amylovora	Other methods	Pathogenicity test			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Pure culture	No	
219	231	Switzerland	Bursaphelenchus	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR for direct detection of BsatF, BsatRV, BsatS, 18S units		qPCR core kit NO ROX Hotgoldstar	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Woody cuttings, Wood	No	
367	232	Italy	Plum pox virus	ELISA	DASI-ELISA (also called TAS ELISA)		PPV Universal ELISA; capture poly	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	No
372	232	Italy	Erwinia amylovora	real-time PCR	Real-time PCR Taqman (Salvi et al. 2007)	P291F, P291R, P291M	SsoAdvanced™ Universal Probes	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
371	232	Italy	Erwinia amylovora	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		Kit Erwinia amylovora; LOEWE®;	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
369	232	Italy	Plum pox virus	real-time RT-PCR	Real-time RT-PCR Taqman	P241, P316M, P316D, TaqMan	SsoAdvanced™ Universal Probes	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
368	232	Italy	Plum pox virus	conventional RT-PCR	Saggio RT-PCR (Wetzel et al. 1991 and 1992)	P1 and P2	GoTaq® DNA Polymerase; PROMEGA	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
359	232	Italy	Citrus tristeza virus	ELISA	DAS-ELISA		CTV Tristeza ELISA, capture poly	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	No
363	232	Italy	Citrus tristeza virus	conventional RT-PCR	Amplification by RT-PCR (OPIN1-PIN2 primers)		GoTaq® DNA Polymerase; PROMEGA	Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttings	Yes	
370	232	Italy	Erwinia amylovora	plating	NSA and CCT medium (Bulletin OEPP/EPPO Bulletin (2013) 43 (1), 21-45)			Both symptomatic and asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Fruit, Herbaceous cuttings	No	
366	232	Italy	Citrus tristeza virus	real-time RT-PCR	Real-time reverse transcription PCR (RT-PCR)	P25F (forward); P25R (reverse)	SsoAdvanced™ Universal Probes	Asymptomatic samples	Leaves, Herbaceous cuttings	No	